

Socioeconomic impact

Economics of hybrid rice seed production in seed growers' fields in Karnataka, India

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The importance of the contribution of India's agricultural sector to national income, employment, and general economic development has been well recognized. The introduction and adoption of technological innovations is one way to increase the productivity. Hybrid rice varieties have been released in Karnataka. Hybrid seed production is an important component of the spread of hybrid rice. We studied the economics and employment generation of seed production in seed growers' fields.

A farmer in Mandya District grew hybrid rice, KRH1, for the Karnataka State Seed Corporation on a contractual

basis, on 0.5 ha under irrigated conditions during the 1996 dry season. The parental seeds were supplied to the farmer from the Regional Research Station through the corporation. Standard seed production techniques were followed. Trained executives of the corporation provided technical guidance.

The hybrid seed yield was 1.5 t ha⁻¹, with a total gross income of Rs 60,000 ha⁻¹ (US\$1=Rs 35), and the corporation procured seed at the rate of Rs 40 kg⁻¹. The cost of cultivation was Rs 24,000 ha⁻¹, including transportation and processing. Thus, the seed production cost was Rs 16 kg⁻¹.

For the total cost of cultivation per hectare, the major costs were labor and bullock pairs (Rs 2,375), followed by fertilizer and plant protection chemicals (Rs 5,985), GA₃ (Rs 2,800), seeds (Rs 1,875), and transportation and processing (Rs 975). The special techniques of seed production, such as leaf clipping, GA₃ application, and rope pulling,

cost Rs 3,825 ha⁻¹. The cost of additional operations such as roguing, separate harvest of A and R lines, among others, was Rs 450 more than for general seed production. For seed production, 150 more men and 55 more women laborers were required for hybrid rice than for inbred varieties. The major operations for these laborers included roguing, rope pulling, leaf clipping, planting, and harvesting. Because the grower also received Rs 2,430 for straw and Rs 8,750 through the sale of restorer grains, gross income was Rs 71,180 ha⁻¹. Thus, the grower received a net income of Rs 47,180 ha⁻¹. This represents a benefit-cost ratio of 1.97.

The study thus indicated that the seed grower can obtain a net profit of Rs 47,180 ha⁻¹ in hybrid rice seed production. Seed production cost Rs 16 kg⁻¹. This activity also generated additional rural employment for 150 men and 55 women. Hybrid seed production is a highly profitable enterprise for willing and innovative farmers. ■

Economics of commercial hybrid rice cultivation

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We studied the economics of the commercial cultivation of KRH1 in Mandya District, Karnataka. This study involved 2 farmers during the 1994 dry season, 5 farmers during the 1994 wet season, and 10 farmers during the 1996 dry season. Means were used for the economic analysis. Rasi was used as a check variety. Plot size ranged from 0.4 to 1.0 ha.

KRH1 yielded 6.5 t ha⁻¹ on average, whereas Rasi yielded 5.0 t ha⁻¹. KRH1 recorded a yield advantage of 1.5 t ha⁻¹. The cost of cultivation of KRH1 was Rs 13,885 (US\$1=Rs 35) vs Rs 12,170 for Rasi. The increased cultivation cost for KRH1 was due to the increased cost of seed and labor for nursery management

and planting. Gross income from KHR1 was Rs 37,500 vs Rs 28,500 from Rasi. KRH1 had an additional gross return of Rs 9,000 ha⁻¹, which resulted in an additional net return of Rs 7,285 ha⁻¹.

It was also observed that the additional labor required for KRH1 lessened with each season as farmers

became more acquainted with new practices such as planting single seedlings hill⁻¹, among others. The benefit-cost ratio for KRH1 was 1.70; it was 1.34 for Rasi. Because the cultivation of KRH1 resulted in an additional net profit of Rs 7,285 ha⁻¹, farmers were impressed by its profit and accepted the new hybrid. ■

Announcement

Scholarships available

IRRI is pleased to announce the availability of an anticipated 14 scholarships to be awarded during 1999 to support highly qualified scientists from rice-growing developing countries interested in pursuing a graduate degree in areas related to rice science. These scholarships include those provided by IRRI (PhD scholarships only) as well as scholarship funds that IRRI administers for other agencies,

primarily the Asian Development Bank (ADB)-Japan scholarship fund (MS and PhD scholarships).

IRRI's overall research effort is divided into seven programs: four focus on ecosystems (irrigated, rainfed, upland, flood-prone), one addresses issues that cut across rice ecosystems (cross ecosystems), one focuses on genetic conservation of rice (genetic resources), and one deals with capacity development of IRRI's partners